

Production of Organic Fertilizer by Vermiculture of Local Earthworms

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Abstract

Earthworm samples were collected from Lan Gwa in Hpa-an, Kayin State. The study period lasted from July 2014 to February 2015. Four earthworm species (*Perionyx exvavatus*, *Pheretima bicincta*, *P. birmanica*, *P. canaliculata*) were detected. Both external reproductive organs and internal features of the body were used as main features for identification. Identification was followed after Gate (1972). Comparison of increased population in different earthworm species was recorded. The population of earthworms was observed to be increased *Perionyx excavates* (299 individuals), *Pheretima birmanica* (327 individuals), *Pheretima canaliculata* (331 individuals) and mix culture of earthworms (398 individuals). Comparison of NPK in vermicompost and vermiwash formed by different earthworm species was observed. Monthly formation of vermicompost and vermiwash and content of pH and NPK was tested during three months. Among them, three month vermicompost possessed the highest quality of pH and NPK but three month vermiwash possessed the highest quality of pH and one and two month vermiwash were the highest quality component of NPK. Efficiency of three different vermicompost formed by mix culture of earthworm monthly was observed to be varied on mustard plant growth rate.

Key word: vermiculture, vermicompost, vermiwash

Introduction

More food is needed to increased population. These foods are obtained from animals and plants. Plants are also obtained by agriculture and horticulture. Agriculture deals with cultivation of crops as well as animal farming, feeding, breeding, and raising livestock. Horticulture is the branch of agriculture. Horticulture may include plants that are not for human consumption (Anonymous, 2009). Fertilizers are essential for growth of plants in both agriculture and horticulture. The essential elements are called nutrients; those needed in the greatest amount are called macronutrients whereas those needed in lesser amounts are called micronutrients.

There are different types of fertilizers. They are commonly classified into (1) chemical or inorganic fertilizer made up with different formulations to suit a variety of specified uses; (2) biofertilizer, a substance which contains living microorganisms; (3) organic fertilizer such as cow manure, bat guano, bone meal, and organic compost and green manure crops (Anonymous, 2014).

Vermiculture is the culture of earthworms. Vermicompost causes reduction of noxious qualities of a wide variety of organic waste, elimination of smell and reduction of harmful microorganisms, production of marketable organic fertilizer, production of aqua life, birds and animal food or even human food by drying earthworms. It also benefits the farmers. It increases soil fertility and bacterial activity, micro grains in the soil and enhances water absorption capacity.

Vermicompost helps the plant root get air easily. That is, vermicompost increases plant resistance to pests, fungus and other diseases (Card *et al.*, 2004).

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Vermicompost can be prepared easily. Vermicomposting is the use of earthworms for composting organic residues (Edwards, 2004).

There are three types of earthworm. These are anecic (out of the earth), endogeic (within the earth), epigeic (upon the earth) worms (Card *et al.*, 2004). Earthworms are segmented invertebrates that inhabit soils and organic wastes. They are hermaphrodites, which mean they have both male and female reproductive organs and usually reproduce by mating, each partner fertilizing the other. There are an estimated 1800 species of earthworm worldwide (Edwards & Lofty, 1977). In nature, the long-time effects of earthworms have certain practical values. In many soil, thousands are present per acre. Darwin (1881) showed that there are on an average, over 53,000 worms in an acre of garden soil.

Earthworms are not only very important to soil fertility but also to need for food of animals such as fish and ducks. So, they are commercial important to gardeners and farmers.

There is no previous study of earthworms in this region, so the present study was carried out with the following objectives;

- to compare the occurrence of earthworms in the study area
- to know the anatomical characteristics of different species
- to investigate the population growth during vermiculture
- to analyze the rate and value of vermicompost formation and vermiwash

Materials and methods

Study area

The location of Hpa-an is situated between latitude $16^{\circ} 30'$ to $17^{\circ} 44'$ north and between longitude $97^{\circ} 21'$ to $98^{\circ} 1'$ east (Fig. 1).

Study period

The study period lasted from July 2014 to February 2015.

Collection and experiment site

Lan Gwa ($16^{\circ} 52' 28.18''$ N and $97^{\circ} 39' 07.10''$ E) was designated for the collection of earthworms in Hpa-an, Kayin State (Plate.1).

Species identification

Identification was followed after Gate (1972).

Preparation for vermiculture, vermicompost and vermiwash

One big bucket (125cm width, 50 cm height) was taken. One hole on the lower most part of the bucket was penetrated by nail. A layer of broken bricks, pieces of stones having thickness of 7-10 cm in the bucket was put. Over this layer put another layer of decomposed leaves having thickness of 7-10 cm. Then, a layer of partially decomposed cow dung having 7-10 cm thickness was put over it. Another layer of decomposed leaves having 7-10 cm thickness was put. After this, a layer of decomposed cow dung having 7-10 cm thickness was put again. Then 15-20 numbers of earthworms were put in the bucket. After that, a layer of cutting banana core having 7-10 cm thickness was giving for earthworm food. The gunny bag covered over the bucket. Water was sprayed regularly for a period of 2-3 days. After 10 days the liquid

vermiwash was produced in the bucket. One little bucket was put under the bottom hole of the bucket. In such a way water falls drop by drop (Plate.2).

Harvesting of vermicompost and counting of earthworms

The numbers of earthworm were counted by hand sorting from the find product of vermicompost used by the mix-culture of earthworm monthly. But the harvesting of vermicompost by *Perionyx excavates*, *P. birmanica*, *P. canaliculata* and counting of the number of earthworms was carried out after three months.

Before harvesting of vermicompost the moisture content was brought down by stopping the addition of water for 3 days.

Physico-chemical content of vermicompost

Each sample of compost One Kilogram was put into a labeled plastic bag and each sample of vermiwash was put into a labeled bottle. These were carried to the laboratory of Land-used Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation in Hpa-an to analyze the chemical contents.

Effect of vermicompost on the plant growth

Effect of vermicompost obtained from mix-culture of earthworm on the plant growth was investigated with mustard (Mon-nyin) seeds. Seedlings of Mon-nyin of same age in plots were measured weekly. Numbers of leaves produced from same age plants sown in different vermicompost were recorded.

Fig. 1 Map of the study areas

(Source: Land use and Survey Department of Hpa-an Township)

A. Collection site

B. Experiment site

Plate 1. Collection and Experiment site

A. Big bucket

B. Broken bricks

C. Decomposed leaves

D. Cow dung

E. Earthworms

F. Cutting banana core

Results

Plate 2. Preparation for vermiculture, Vermicompost and vermiwash
A total of 4 species belonging to 2 genera of some earthworms were recorded

A. Life specimen of *Perionyx excavatus*

B. Peristomium of
P. excavates

C. Life specimen of *Pheretima bicincta*

D. Peristomium of *P. bicincta*

E. Life specimen of *Pheretima birmanica*

F. Peristomium of
P. birmanica

G. Life specimen of *Pheretima canaliculata*

H. Peristomium of *P.*
canaliculata

Plate 3. Distinct external characters of studied earthworm species

A. Spermathecal pores of
Perionyx excavatus

B. Seminal vesicles and
intestine of *P. excavatus*

C. Male pores of *Pheretima bicincta*

D. Gizzard, intestine and caecum
of *P. bicincta*

E. Male pores of *Pheretima birmanica*

F. Spermathecae, seminal vesicles
and caecum of *P. birmanica*

G. Male pores of *Pheretima canaliculata*

H. Last heart and caecum of
P. canaliculata

Plate 4. Distinct internal characters of studied earthworm species

A. Vermicompost

B. Vermiwash

C. Mustard (Mon-nyin)

Plate 5. Vermicompost, Vermiwash and Mustard plant

Table 1. External distinctive characters of studied earthworms

No.	External	<i>Perionyx excavatus</i>	<i>Pheretima bicincta</i>	<i>Pheretima birmanica</i>	<i>Pheretima canaliculata</i>
1.	Length	50-180 mm	40-80mm	100-160mm	147mm
2.	Segment	115-178	77-101	112	111
3.	Clitellum	XIII-XVII	XIV-XVI	XIV-XVI	XIV-XVI
4.	Spermathecal pore	7/8,8/9	5/6,6/7,7/8,8/9	5/6-7/8	Large, 5/6-7/8
5.	Male pore	XVIII	XVIII	XVIII	XVIII minute
6.	Female pore	XIV	XIV	XIV	XIV median
7.	First dorsal pore	4/5or 5/6	12/13	12/13	7/9
8.	Genital marking	Absent	Present, XVIII 18/19, papillae (paired)	None	Present, one pair disc-like
9.	Prostomium	Epilobous	Epilobous	Epilobous	Epilobous

Table 2. Internal distinctive characters of studied earthworms

No.	Internal	<i>Perionyx excavatus</i>	<i>Pheretima bicincta</i>	<i>Pheretima birmanica</i>	<i>Pheretima canaliculata</i>
1.	Septa	7/8/9 slightly thickened	5/6-7/8,8/9 aborted, 9/10-12/13 muscular to thickly muscular	5/6-6/7 thickened, 8/9-9/10 aborted	9/10 aborted, 8/9 membranous, 10/11 very delicate
2.	Gizzard location	VI vestigial	9-10	9-10	8-9
3.	Last heart	XIII	XII	XIII	XIII
4.	Seminal vesicle	IX-XII	XI-XII	XI-XII small	XI,XII large
5.	Intestinal beginning	XVI	XV	XV	XV
6.	Genital marking gland	Absent	Present , 17-18	Lacking	Present one mass without stalks for each marking
7.	<i>Prostate gland</i>	XVIII	XVI-XIX	XVI-XX	XVII-XX ducts short, stout, straight or l-shaped
8.	Caecum location	absent	XXI-XXII, simple, small	XXVII-XXVIII	XXVII-XXV shortest
9.	Spermathecae location	8,9	6,7,8,9	6,7,8	5,6,7,8

Table 3. Monthly population growth and size of the mixed culture of earthworms during vermiculture

Time Duration	Initial number	Increased number	Smallest size	Largest size
After one month	20	47	1.1cm	7.95 cm
After two month	20	219	1.13 cm	10 cm
After three month	20	310	1.49 cm	11.1 cm
After four month	20	329	1.81 cm	12.2 cm

Fig. 2 Monthly population growth and size of the mixed culture of earthworms during vermiculture

Table 4. Monthly rate of vermicompost formation and value of pH and content of NPK formed from mixed culture of earthworm during experiment

Time duration	Vermicompost weight	pH	N %	P2O5 %	K2O %
After one month	22kg	7.71	0.62	0.61	0.43
After two month	20 kg	7.30	0.78	0.88	0.40
After three month	19kg	7.76	0.48	0.98	0.40
After four month	19kg	7.52	0.50	0.98	0.28

Fig. 3 Monthly rate of vermicompost formation and value of pH and content of NPK formed from mixed culture of earthworm during experiment

Table 5. Monthly formation of vermiwash formed from mixed culture of earthworm and value of pH and content of NPK in vermiwash during experiment

Time duration	Value of pH and content of NPK in vermiwash			
	pH	N %	P ₂ O ₅ %	K ₂ O %
After one month	7.89	0.56	0.01	0.03
After two month	7.78	0.56	0.01	0.03
After three month	7.46	0.01	Nil	0.03

Fig. 4 Monthly formation of vermiwash formed from mixed culture of earthworm and value of pH and content of NPK in vermiwash during experiment

Table 6. Comparison of increased population and growth rate in different earthworm species during experiment

Different kinds of earthworm	During experiment			
	Initial number	Increased number	After three month growth rate	
			Smallest size	Largest size
<i>Perionyx excavatus</i>	20	299	1.66cm	2.68cm
<i>Pheretima birmanica</i>	20	327	1.78cm	3.18cm
<i>Pheretima canaliculata</i>	20	331	1.64cm	2.38cm
Mix culture of earthworm	20	398	1.9cm	6.02cm

Fig.5 Comparison of increased population and growth rate in different earthworm species during experiment

Table 7. The rate of vermicompost formation and value of vermicompost formed from different kinds of earthworms

Different kind of earthworms	Vermicompost weight	Value of pH and content of NPK in vermicompost			
		pH	N %	P %	K %
<i>Perionyx excavatus</i>	20 kg	7.25	0.59	1.33	0.25
<i>Pheretima birmanica</i>	20 kg	7.11	0.58	1.03	0.36
<i>Pheretima canaliculata</i>	20kg	7.14	1.01	1.09	0.44
Mix culture of earthworm	22kg	6.66	0.501	0.96	0.29

Fig.6 The rate of vermicompost formation and value of vermicompost formed from different kinds of earthworms

Table 8. Weekly growth rate of mustard plant in three different vermicompost formed by mixed culture of earthworm

Period	After one month vermicompost		After two month vermicompost		After three month vermicompost		Control	
	Height (cm)	No. of leaves	Height (cm)	No. of leaves	Height (cm)	No. of leaves	Height (cm)	No. of leaves
1 st week	2.8cm	2.00	2.1cm	2.00	3.3cm	2.00	1.1cm	2.00
2 nd week	4.2cm	3.00	4.2cm	3.00	5cm	3.00	2.95cm	3.00
3 rd week	4.6cm	4.00	4.2cm	4.00	5cm	4.00	3.1cm	4.00
4 th week	4.7cm	4.00	4.3cm	4.00	5.1cm	4.00	3.5cm	4.00
5 th week	5.0cm	5.00	4.5cm	5.00	5.5cm	5.00	3.6cm	4.00
6 th week	6.7cm	5.00	8.4cm	5.00	7.10cm	5.00	5cm	4.00
7 th week	7cm	5.00	9.5cm	5.00	8cm	5.00	6cm	4.00

Fig. 7 Weekly growth rate of mustard plant in three different vermicompost formed by mixed culture of earthworm

Discussion

Earthworms are terrestrial invertebrates with thousands of species grouped into three categories according to their behavior in the natural environment: anecic (out of the earth), endogeic (within the earth) and epigeic (upon the earth) (Card *et al.*, 2004). In the present study, the earthworms were collected from the surface litter of Lan Gwa for vermicomposting of local earthworms. Therefore, the collected earthworms are epigeic.

A total of 4 species belonging to 2 genera of earthworms were recorded. These species were *Perionyx exvavatus*, *Pheretima bicincta*, *P. birmanica*, *P. canaliculata*. The genus was identified by using color and clitellum. *Perionyx* were red in color and *Pheretima* were purple in color. *Perionyx* was smaller than *Pheretima*. The clitellum of *Perionyx* was from XIII to XVII and that of *Pheretima* from XIV to XVI. Therefore, the genus was easily distinguished externally. Moreover, species were identified by genital marking.

During first experiment, after two month and three month the number of individuals was different. But nearly the same number of individuals after three month and four month was found. So, the earthworm was raised after three month very enough.

Earthworms commonly found in agricultural fields thrive at neutral pH, but can tolerate a pH from 5.0 to 8.0. Worms can survive in pH 5 to 9 and prefer pH 7 or slightly higher. Optimum was 7.5 to 8.0 (Edward, 1998). In present study, the range of vermicompost formed from mixed culture of earthworm monthly was pH 7.30 to 7.76. So, earthworms prefer the result vermicompost.

Vermicompost tea (vermiwash) can be used in a wide range of horticultural and agricultural systems to elicit plant growth and pest and disease management responses through a variety of mechanisms (Edwards, 2010). In the present study, the liquid vermiwash was produced in the bucket. Small bucket was put under the bottom hole of the bucket. In such a way water falls drop by drop. Monthly formation of vermiwash formed from mix culture of earthworm and content of pH and NPK was tested during first experiment.

Both white and brown mustard are grown as spring-sown annual crops whose dry seeds are harvested in early autumn. So, quality of vermicompost was tested by the growth of mustard in the present study. Nitrogen is the leaf and stem developer and adding nitrogen will get thing growing fast. Phosphorus is valuable for developing flowers and fruit plus helps roots take quickly to the soil around them. Potassium promotes healthy roots systems and helps the plants resist disease (Anonymous, 2010). In the present study, growth rate of mustard plant that sown in two month vermicompost was highest in all plants due to the content of N was more than others.

Conclusion

In conclusion, advantages of the raising of earthworms are fish hatcheries, poultry growers buy worms as feed for animals and private laboratories, universities, and high schools use worms for research and classroom needs. Therefore, earthworm growers can make money by selling earthworms. The chemical fertilizers are replaced by use of vermicompost as organic fertilizer to increase the yield of vegetables and crops.

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